

POLYMERISED MEDIUM INTERNAL PHASE EMULSIONS AS STRUCTURAL SEPARATORS

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Keywords: multifunctional materials, macroporous polymers, medium internal phase emulsion, deep eutectic solvent, supercapacitor

ABSTRACT

To achieve true multifunctionality of the energy storage device, all elements of it have to be able to perform two roles simultaneously. Currently most related research is focused on the development and/or improvement of electrodes and electrolyte while research into the separator is rather limited. Here, the feasibility of using polymerised non-aqueous medium internal phase emulsions (polyMIPEs), based on Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA), as separators for structural supercapacitors is presented. To ensure ion conduction in the separator a deep eutectic solvent (DES), based on choline chloride (ChCl) and ethylene glycol (EG), was used as an internal phase in the studied systems. The effect of surfactant concentration and rate of internal phase addition on the properties, such as ionic conductivity and compressive properties, and microstructure of the resulting polyMIPEs were investigated. Increasing the surfactant concentration led to the formation of a less defined microstructure with a wider pore size distribution, increased ionic conductivity and reduced mechanical performance, as well as an improved tolerance towards variations in drop rate of internal phase (DES) addition. It was found that the minimum drop rate for MIPE preparation was 0.39 ml/min and further reduction led to the formation of large air bubbles/defects. The change in morphology meant that polyMIPEs stabilised by 20 wt% surfactant exhibited lower ionic conductivity and mechanical properties across the systems investigated. PolyMIPEs with an ionic conductivity of 1.9 mS/cm, which is only 4 times lower than the ionic conductivity of the neat DES (7.58 mS/cm), and a compressive modulus of 0.21 GPa were achieved.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years there has been significant increase in research activities focusing on multifunctional materials and devices [1], especially multifunctional energy storage devices such as supercapacitors and batteries [2]. This is because energy storage is one of the areas where the introduction of multifunctional materials is expected to save weight and volume by combining the features of structural integrity with electrochemical performance [2]. This paper focuses on supercapacitors since they offer a compromise in terms of energy and power density performance. The main components of conventional supercapacitors include electrodes, electrolyte and separator. For an energy device to be truly multifunctional its main components have to perform two roles, conventional, i.e. related to electrochemical performance of the supercapacitor, and structural.

However, despite the progress achieved in this area, most of the research has focused on materials for electrodes and electrolyte. One of the components of the supercapacitor which has received far less attention to-date is the separator. The separator material has to fulfil number of criteria: they have to be porous, electrically insulating but ionically permeable. In addition, to be used in structural supercapacitors, separator material should also have a good interface with structural electrolyte and be suitable for composite manufacturing process. In our research to date few separator materials, woven

and unwoven mats, impregnated with structural electrolyte (i.e. multifunctional electrolyte or multifunctional matrix) were used [3-4] in combination with carbon fibre mats as electrodes. However, the presence of the separator adds to the complexity of the multifunctional composite and could increase the chance of delamination. Creating a separator which would not require an additional support, in the form of a woven/non-woven mat, having a good interface with carbon fibres, and containing an electrolyte, would resolve a number of issues some of which are briefly mentioned above.

Porosity is one of the main characteristics of a separator and there are number of techniques for achieving polymers with a porous structure which can be divided into templating and non-templating. Non-templating mainly relies on phase separation during the reaction with the resulting microstructure of polymers varying significantly from submicron to micron [5-6]. Templating, as name suggests, requires a template to create a porous structure. One of the examples of templating is an emulsion templating in which, by varying the amount of the internal phase, it is possible to control the porosity of the resulting macroporous polymer. Emulsions prepared using at least 74 vol.% of internal phase are called high internal phase emulsions (HIPE) [7]; if amount of the internal phase varies between 40-74 vol.% the resulting emulsion is called a medium internal phase emulsion (MIPE) [8]. To formulate emulsions two immiscible phases are mixed together, after the internal phase is added dropwise into the continuous phase, in the presence of surfactant. HIPEs and MIPEs can be solidified using a range of mechanisms, from radical polymerisation to thiol-ene chemistry. [9-11] Resulting macroporous polymers have low density, high porosity and mechanical properties which can be varied by changing the composition of the HIPE or MIPE and preparation procedure, such as stirring rate and the rate of addition of the internal phase. [12] Even though HIPEs and polyHIPEs based on styrene and divinyl benzene are still the most studied systems, the number of the monomers used in emulsion templating is steadily growing [9]. The majority of the reported emulsion templates contain aqueous solutions of the various inorganic salts but non-aqueous systems are starting to attract increased attention as they allow a widening of the type of the reactions for use in solidification of MIPE. Another reason is that conventionally, the internal phase is removed after solidification/polymerisation to obtain macroporous polymers; however, for some applications the presence of the internal phase inside the resulting polymers is essential. [13]

Earlier we have shown [13] that polyHIPEs filled with ionic liquid (IL) could potentially be used as separators in lithium ion batteries. The choice of IL as the internal phase was made based on the combination of properties; including high ionic conductivity, high thermal stability, negligible vapour pressure and the ability to dissolve a variety of materials of different nature. Unfortunately, despite the combination of these unique properties, concerns were raised regarding ILs' cost and biodegradability. [14]. At the same time, research into deep-eutectic solvents (DES) as an alternative to IL, especially for chemical synthesis, showed a significant growth. Even though DES and ILs do not share the same chemical properties, they have similar physical properties; in particular they both offer a low vapor pressure, wide liquid range and relatively high ionic conductivity [15]. DES contain large, nonsymmetric ions that have low melting points, and may be obtained using the large depression of the freezing point when combining ammonium salts with metal chlorides or hydrogen donors [15-16]. Other attractive properties of DES include low cost, straightforward synthesis, low toxicity, biocompatibility, and biodegradability [17]. DES are eutectic mixtures formed through association of hydrogen bond donors and ammonium or phosphonium salts. The properties of DES can be tailored by the starting materials and their ratios. [18] It was shown that DES could be used as an internal phase for preparation of HIPEs [19] using acrylic monomers in continuous phase, and no specific application was mentioned.

The choice of the composition of the continuous phase is more straightforward, taking into account the final application of the separator in question. Using epoxy based continuous phase will provide the required mechanical properties and would insure compatibility with carbon fibres. The literature discussing epoxy based polyHIPEs available is rather limited [20-21] and to the best of our knowledge does not include non-aqueous systems which are desirable if separators are to use in supercapacitors.

Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) was chosen as a main component of the continuous phase as it is a commonly studied epoxy resin that, when cured with isophorone diamine (iPDA), displays a

higher Young's modulus than other combinations of DGEBA and hardener, with a value of 2.65 GPa [22].

The research presented here concerns non-aqueous MIPes (with internal phase volume of 50 vol%) and polyMIPes based on DGEBA, and containing DES based on choline chloride (ChCl) and ethylene glycol (EG). The choice of the MIPE instead of HIPE was made to achieve a better balance between ionic conductivity provided by the internal phase, i.e. DES, and mechanical properties provided by DGEBA. The effect of the MIPE formulations and preparation conditions on properties of the resulting polyMIPes was studied and the potential for using the resulting polyMIPes as separators for supercapacitors is discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA), 5-amino-1,3,3-trimethylcyclohexanemethylamine, mixture of cis and trans (isophorone diamine (iPDA), $\geq 99.0\%$), choline chloride (ChCl, $\geq 98.0\%$) and ethylene glycol (EG, 99.8%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used as received. The surfactants Cithrol DPHS-SO-(MV) (Cithrol), Hypermer B246 (H246) were kindly provided by Croda.

2.2 Sample preparation

2.2.1. DES preparation

The DES was synthesised by mixing ChCl and EG in 1:3 molar ratio [18] at 80 °C and constant stirring for 24 hours. The ionic conductivity of DES formed was determined to be 7.58 mS/cm, which is in agreement with the value of 7.61 mS/cm reported in the literature [18].

2.2.2. MIPE/polyMIPE preparation

MIPes were prepared in a glass reaction vessel equipped with a glass paddle rod connected to an overhead stirrer. The continuous phase was prepared by dissolving surfactant in the hardener and after a uniform solution was formed the epoxy was added, ensuring the molar ratio of DGEBA to IPD was 2:1. The mixture was stirred using an overhead stirrer at 400 rpm until a homogeneous solution was obtained. Following this, internal phase (DES) (50 vol.%) was added dropwise under continuous stirring at 500 rpm. After all the internal phase was added, the stirring rate was increased to 1000 rpm over a 30 second period and then mixed at this speed for 90 seconds to further homogenise the emulsion. The prepared emulsions were transferred into polypropylene centrifuge tubes with diameter 25 mm. The MIPes were polymerised using the following curing cycle:

- (1) ramp to 60 °C at 2 °C·min⁻¹;
- (2) hold at 60 °C for 1 hour ;
- (3) ramp to 80 °C at 3 °C·min⁻¹;
- (4) hold at 80 °C for 2 hours;
- (5) cooled down to r.t.

The samples were then removed from their molds and post cured

- (1) ramp to 120 °C at 6 °C·min⁻¹;
- (2) hold at 120 °C for 2 hours.

Samples were cooled in the oven to r.t. prior to their removal.

2.3 Sample characterisation

The as-synthesised polyMIPes were used to determine ionic conductivity and mechanical properties but DES was extracted and polyMIPes were dried to study morphology. For DES extraction the sample was cut, placed into the glass vial and submerged in ethanol. To increase the rate of diffusion the solvent (ethanol) was exchanged twice a day for one week. After this the solvent was decanted and the sample dried in a vacuum oven at 70 °C under reduced pressure to constant weight.

Impedance spectroscopy was used to determine *the ionic conductivity* (σ) of polyMIPes as-synthesised. Experiments were carried out using VersaSTAT 3-450 potentiostat on discs cut from the top and bottom of monoliths. The measurements were conducted at room temperature in a frequency range from 250 kHz to 1 Hz and an amplitude of the sinusoidal voltage of 5 mV. The ionic conductivity (σ) was calculated on the basis of sample dimensions and bulk resistance (R_b) values which were determined from the high frequency intercept of the impedance curve with the real axis using the following relationship:

$$\sigma = \frac{h}{R_b}. \quad (1)$$

The mechanical performance of the polyMIPes was determined through uniaxial compression tests [23], carried out according to the industrial standard ASTM D1621-2004.

The morphology of the polyMIPes was studied after the extraction of the internal phase using scanning electron microscopy (FEI Helios Nanolab 600), with an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. All samples were gold coated in an argon atmosphere to guarantee sufficient electrical conductivity.

2.4. Supercapacitor manufacture and characterisation

Structural supercapacitors were made by placing a film of MIPE between two carbon fibre mats containing copper tape as a current collector and cured using the curing cycle described for MIPes in 2.2.1. The electrochemical performance of the device was studied using cyclic voltammetry (CV) with the help of a VersaSTAT 3-450 potentiostat. A frequency range from 200 kHz to 10 mHz, and a potential amplitude of 10 mV was used. Five different scan rates were employed from 5 to 25 mV·s⁻¹.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Effect of surfactant concentration on the microstructure, ionic conductivity, and mechanical properties

PolyMIPes were successfully synthesised using surfactant concentrations of 15, 17.5, and 20 wt%. Several attempts to make MIPes using lower surfactant concentrations (5 and 10 wt%) were unsuccessful, as emulsion viscosity decreased instantaneously after only partial addition of the DES, indicating phase inversion. This was similar to a different study on polyHIPEs by Yang *et al* [24], in which it was concluded that decreasing the surfactant concentration in the aqueous based HIPEs, increases the interfacial tension and reduces the overall stability of the emulsion. Increase of the surfactant concentration above 20 wt% was not possible as viscosity of the solution of the surfactant in the hardener (iPDA) was too high for MIPE preparation.

Apart from the surfactant concentration, the stability of the MIPE also depends on other factors such as drop rate of the internal phase addition. It was observed that using a drop rate that was too low or too high led to emulsion destabilisation before all internal phase was added. Further investigation found that the optimum drop rate depends on the surfactant concentration and has to be found separately for each formulation in the studied systems. For samples of total volume of 40 ml, to achieve polymerisable MIPE, the drop rate should be kept to a minimum of 0.59, 0.41, and 0.39 ml/min for surfactant concentration of 15, 17.5, and 20 wt%, respectively. It can be seen that increasing the surfactant concentration decreased the drop rate resulting in polymerisable MIPE. It is reasonable to assume that there are number of parameters responsible for the observed relationship, for example increasing the surfactant content leads to improvement of the emulsion stability or/and viscosity of the reaction mixture. It is important to note that the optimal drop rate depends also on sample size; it was observed that when the volume of MIPE was smaller than 40 ml, using the same drop rate found for the 40 ml volume did not resulted in MIPE formation.

Fig 1. SEM micrographs of DGEBA based polyMIPES prepared using different surfactant concentration: a – 15 wt%; b – 17.5 wt%; c – 20 wt%.

Fig. 1 shows the dependence of the microstructure of the resulting polyMIPES on surfactant content. All polyMIPES have regions of a conventional polyMIPE microstructure, i.e. interconnected pores with pore throats. However, all samples showed broad pore size distribution (Fig 2) due to the presence of large pores /voids (SEM images are not presented here). Similar results were reported in the literature [25], where the use of Cithrol to stabilise non-aqueous HIPEs led to the formation of a hierarchical pore morphology where large pores were surrounded by pores of two orders of magnitude smaller. The “skin” effect seen at the boundaries of these large pores/voids suggests that they could be air bubbles. It is possible to suggest that skin formation occurs due to the development of epoxy rich regions at an interface. Here the surface layer becomes denser and more closed than the bulk of the material.

Fig 2. Normalised pore size distribution using a surfactant concentration of 15, 17.5 and 20 wt%

Comparison of SEM images shows that as the surfactant concentration is increased the microstructure becomes increasingly less uniform. This is supported in the literature where increasing the surfactant concentration is reported to cause the formation of less defined strut like microstructures [25-27]. Note, the majority of the literature available discusses polyHIPE systems, but it is reasonable to assume that trends in the relationships observed would be the same for polyMIPES. Research undertaken by Cameron *et al.* [28], theorised that a decrease in droplet diameter occurs with an increase in stability, as the lower interfacial tension permits a larger interfacial area. This would imply that increasing the surfactant concentration leads to a decrease in pore diameter; however, the opposite

was observed both here and in a study undertaken by Shirshova *et al.* on non-aqueous polyHIPEs with ionic liquid as the internal phase [27].

The surfactant concentration can be seen to influence a number of other factors as summarised in Table 1. Increasing the surfactant concentration caused the ionic conductivity to rise from 0.7 to 3.8 mS/cm, a trend also observed in a further study on polyHIPE systems that used ionic liquid as the internal phase [27]. It is possible to use similar arguments as made previously [28, 13], that the relationship between surfactant concentration and properties of the resulting polyMIPEs is due to a decrease in the pore and pore throat sizes with the lowered surfactant content, reducing the overall interconnectivity of the polyMIPE.

Surfactant concentration, wt%	Ionic conductivity, mS/cm	Elastic modulus, GPa	Compressive strength, MPa
15	0.70 ± 0.05	0.24 ± 0.03	14.8 ± 0.6
17.5	1.90 ± 0.20	0.21 ± 0.02	12.3 ± 0.6
20	3.80 ± 0.15	0.18 ± 0.02	10.0 ± 0.2

Table I. Effect of the surfactant concentration on polyMIPE ionic conductivity and mechanical properties

The results presented in Table 1 also show an inverse relationship between the mechanical properties and surfactant concentration, which agrees with the trend observed by Cameron *et al.* [28] for polyHIPEs systems. One explanation for the observed trend is that upon increase of surfactant concentration interconnectivity of resulting polyMIPEs or polyHIPEs increases and the thickness of the walls of the pores decreases, reducing the mechanical properties. Graeber [12] suggested that the solubility of a surfactant within the resultant polymer could have a significant impact on the mechanical properties. Surfactants are molecules that possess both hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups, or in the case of this study are lipophilic /lipophobic; thus they can diffuse from the phase they are dissolved in to the interface between the two phases. It was suggested that any surfactant that is not fully embedded within the polymer could have a plasticising effect [12]. Another relationship which can be seen in the Table 1 is an inverse relationship between mechanical properties and ionic conductivity, which is in good agreement with the literature [5, 6].

3.2. Effect of the drop rate and mixing speed on the properties of the resulting polyMIPE

During the optimisation process it became apparent that the system was sensitive to both the mixing speed and the drop rate of the internal phase addition, as was briefly mentioned earlier. A relatively small reduction of the drop rate from 0.41 to 0.39 ml/min led to significant changes in the properties of the resulting polyMIPEs. The reason for this drastic change in properties is still to be found.

Drop rate, ml/min	Ionic conductivity, mS/cm	Elastic modulus, GPa	Compressive strength, MPa
0.39	0.9 ± 0.1	0.01 ± 0.002	8.5 ± 0.3
0.41	3.8 ± 0.2	0.18 ± 0.02	10.0 ± 0.2

Table 2. Effect of drop rate on polyMIPE properties synthesised using 20 wt% of surfactant

Using the lowest value of optimum drop rate possible to avoid emulsion destabilisation (0.39 ml/min), significantly reduced the mechanical properties and ionic conductivity. This is likely due to a change in the microstructure (not presented here) as large voids of mm size could be observed even on the surface of the polyMIPE upon visual inspection. SEM images of samples made with a drop rate of 0.39 ml/min, presented (SEM images are not shown here), showed an increase in the average pore size

and pore size distribution, with a significant increase in the size and occurrence of voids with diameters larger than 20 μm . The average void size was calculated to be $130 \pm 98 \mu\text{m}$, and $56 \pm 35 \mu\text{m}$ using a drop rate of 0.39 ml/min, and 0.41 ml/min, respectively. It is possible that the increased void size, indicates a reduction of emulsion stability, as Mira *et al* [31] found that large droplets mean the system is closer to the inversion state.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Non-aqueous epoxy based polyMIPes were investigated for their potential as structural separators in the construction of structural supercapacitors. The effects of the surfactant concentration and drop rate on the resulting ionic conductivity, mechanical properties, and morphology were explored. Increasing the surfactant concentration led to a less defined microstructure with a larger pore size distribution, increased ionic conductivity, decreased mechanical properties, and reduced optimum drop rate. Using a drop rate that was too low significantly affected the microstructure, increasing the size and occurrence of voids/air bubbles. The change in morphology meant that PolyMIPes (stabilised by 20 wt% surfactant) saw a decrease in their ionic conductivity and elastic modulus from 3.8 to 0.9 mS/cm, and 180 to 0.12 MPa, respectively.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Funding from the EPSRC grant EP/P007465/1 is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] L.E. Asp, E.S. Greenhalgh. Structural Power Composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, 101, 41–61, 2014.
- [2] C. González, J.J. Vilatela, J.M. Molina-Aldareguía, C.S. Lopes, J. LLorca. “Structural composites for multifunctional applications: Current challenges and future trends”. *Progress in Materials Science*, 89, 194–251., 2017.
- [3] H. Qian, A. R. Kucernak, E. S. Greenhalgh, A. Bismarck, M. S. P Shaffer, “Multifunctional structural supercapacitor composites based on carbon aerogel modified high performance carbon fibre fabrics,” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 5 (13), 6113-6122, 2013.
- [4] N. Shirshova H. Qian, M. Houille, Q. Fontana, J.H.G. Steinke, A.R.J. Kucernak, E. Greenhalgh, A. Bismarck, M.S.P. Shaffer., “Multifunctional structural energy storage composite supercapacitors,” *Faraday Discussion*, 172, 81– 103, 2014.
- [5] N. Shirshova et al., “Composition as a means to control morphology and properties of epoxy based dual-phase structural electrolytes,” *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 118 (49), 28377–28387, 2014.
- [6] [7] N. Shirshova *et al*, “Structural supercapacitor electrolytes based on bicontinuous ionic liquid–epoxy resin systems,” *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 1 (48), 15300, 2013.
- [7] M.S. Silverstein, “PolyHIPes: Recent advances in emulsion templated porous polymers,” *Progress in Polym. Sci.*, 39 (1), 199-234, 2014.
- [8] R. Wu, A. Menner, A. Bismarck. “Macroporous polymers made from medium internal phase emulsion templates: Effect of emulsion formulation on the pore structure of polyMIPes”. *Polymer*, 54 (21), 5511-5517, 2013.
- [9] M.S. Silverstein, “Emulsion-templated polymers: Contemporary contemplations”, *Polymer*, 126, 261-282, 2017.
- [10] M. Paljevac, J. Kotek, K. Jeřábek, Peter Krajnc, “Influence of Topology of Highly Porous Methacrylate Polymers on their Mechanical Properties,” *Macromol. Mater. Eng.*, 303, 1700337 (8 pages), 2018.
- [11] C. Chen, A.M. Eissa, T.L. Schiller, N.R. Cameron, “Emulsion-templated porous polymers prepared by thiol-ene and thiol-yne photopolymerisation using multifunctional acrylate and non-acrylate monomers”, *Polymer*, 126, 395-401, 2017.

- [12]N. Graeber, "A study of fundamentals in emulsion templating for the preparation of macroporous polymer foams," Ph.D dissertation, Dept. Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London, 2013, [Online]. Available: <https://spiral.imperial.ac.uk/handle/10044/1/27245>.
- [13]N. Shirshova, P. Johansson, M.J. Marczewski, E. Kot, D. Ensling, A. Bismarck, J.H.G. Steinke, "Polymerised high internal phase ionic liquid-in oil emulsions as potential separators for lithium ion batteries," *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 1 (34), 9612 - 9619, 2013.
- [14]Y. Yu, X. Lu, Q. Zhou, K. Dong, H. Yao, S. Zhang, "Biodegradable naphthenic acid ionic liquids: Synthesis, characterization, and quantitative structure-biodegradation relationship," *Chemistry - A European Journal A*, 14 (35), 11174–11182, 2008.
- [15]E.L. Smith, A.P. Abbott, S.K. Ryder, "Deep Eutectic Solvents (DESS) and Their Applications," *Chemical Reviews*, 114 (21), 2014.
- [16]M. Figueiredo, C. Gomes, R. Costa, A. Martins, C. M. Pereira, F. Silva, "Differential capacity of a deep eutectic solvent based on choline chloride and glycerol on solid electrodes," *Electrochim. Acta*, 54 (9), 2630-2634, 2009.
- [17]J.G Lynam, N. Kumar, M. J. Wong, "Deep eutectic solvents' ability to solubilize lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose; thermal stability; and density," *Bioresource Technology*, 238, 684-689, 2017.
- [18]A.P. Abbott, R.C. Harris, and K.S. Ryder, "Application of hole theory to define ionic liquids by their transport properties," *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 111 (18), 4910–4913, 2007.
- [19]Carranza, K. Song, J.F.A. Soltero-Martínez, Q. Wu, J.A. Pojman, J.D. Mota-Morales, "On the stability and chemorheology of a urea choline chloride deep-eutectic solvent as an internal phase in acrylic high internal phase emulsions", *RSC Adv.*, 6, 81694- 81702, 2016
- [20]R. Rezanavaz, C.J. Fee, S. Dimartino, "GMA-based emulsiontemplated solid foams: Influence of co-crosslinker on morphology and mechanical properties," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 135 (21), 46295, 2018.
- [21]S. Jerenec, M. Šimic, A. Savnik, A. Podgornik, M. Kolar, M. Turnšek. P. Krajnc, "Glycidyl methacrylate and ethylhexyl acrylate based polyHIPE monoliths: Morphological, mechanical and chromatographic properties", *Reactive & Functional Polymers*, 78, 32-37, 2014.
- [22]F.G. Garcia, B.G. Soares, V.J.R.R. Pita, R. Sánchez, J. Rieumont, "Mechanical properties of epoxy networks based on DGEBA and aliphatic amines," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 106 (3), 2047–2055, 2007.
- [23]ASTM D1621-10, Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Rigid Cellular Plastics, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2010.
- [24]H. Yang, F. Zhang, S. Zhang, and J. Chen, "Interconnected porous material prepared via high internal phase emulsion stabilized by mixture of Fe₃O₄ and Tween 85," *MATEC Web of Conferences*, vol. 67, 06097, Jan. 2016.
- [25]E. Kot, N. Shirshova, A. Bismarck, and J.H.G. Steinke, "Nonaqueous high internal phase emulsion templates for synthesis of macroporous polymers *in situ* filled with cyclic carbonate electrolytes," *RCS Advances*, 4, 11512-11519, 2014.
- [26]Z. Bhumgara, "PolyHIPE foam materials as filtration media," *Filtration and Separation*, 32 (3), 245-251, 1995.
- [27]N. Shirshova, A. Bismarck and J. H. G. Steinke, "Ionic Liquids as Internal Phase for Non-Aqueous PolyHIPEs," *Macromolecular Rapid Communications*, 32, 1899–1904, 2011.
- [28]Cameron, Neil R, "High internal phase emulsion templating as a route to well-defined porous polymers," *Polymer*, 46(5), 1439-1449, 2005.
- [29]I. Mira *et al*, "Emulsion catastrophic inversion from abnormal to normal morphology. 2. effect of the stirring intensity on the dynamic inversion frontier," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 42 (1), 57–61, 2003.